

CALCULATION METHODICS OF THIN-WALLED CONSTRUCTIONS MADE OF COMPOSITE MATERIALS

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ABSTRACT

The described methodics presents one of the variants of the applied composite shells theory. It permitted to obtain relationships for determining normal and shear stresses and also for stiffness or modulus of elasticity a hybrid multilayer beam and thin-walled structures made of composite materials. Mentioned relationship are good for practical usage, especially in the stage of sketch designing, taking into account non-linear diagrams of materials deformation. Dependences for calculations of stiff hybrid constructions, both at bending and tension, were obtained which allow to optimize the geometry of structures attaining the minimum weight. The developed program for the calculation of thin-walled structures of composite materials allows the actual consideration of the role of every element during the operation to outside loading factors without any preliminary analyses. Calculation of stiffness and strength characteristics of cross-reinforced composite materials is carried out in accordance with the well-know mechanical characteristics of a mono-layer that are estimated experimentally.

Keywords: composite material, tension, compression, shear, beam, thin-walled shell, structural strength.

1. INTRODUCTION

Engineering theory of a beam has been developed for more than three centuries and at present is of great importance to solid-state mechanics [1]. Computations of structures made of different composite materials are often carried out on the basis of models of laminated media. Laminated structures mechanics is known for the different ways to present a problem and various methods to solve it. In most cases the improved theories that bring a three dimensional problem to a one dimensional one (for beams) or two dimensional one (for plates and shells) are precise enough to determine the integral characteristics (deflection, critical loads, frequency of natural oscillations) of laminated beams, plates and shells. Improved first order theories, e.g. theories a la Timoshenko, based on the linear approximation of displacements usually, do not specify the value of stresses in general as compared

to the classical theory of Kirchhoff-Liaw, but specify only the values of constructions integral characteristics /2/.

It is a well-known fact /3/ that there exist two kinds of approach for solving the problems of deformed laminated constructions. On the one hand it is an exact approach based on the solutions of the theory of elasticity; on the other hand the approximated approaches based on the hypotheses of the displacement distribution or stress fields of transverse coordinates. Examples of applications of these approaches are given elsewhere /4/. Consequently, it is necessary to confirm and, if needed, to improve the applied theories or specify the range of their application on the basis of the investigation of adequate mathematical models.

2. ANALYSIS OF THE STRESS-STRAINED STATE OF MULTILAYERED HYBRID BEAM

The present paper presents a handy method, as concerns the engineering practice, for the stiffness and strength calculation of hybrid multi-layered beams taking into account the module heterogeneity and non-linearity of deformation diagram. The statical behaviour of the construction under minor deformations, including the transverse shearing deformation, are analysed as well.

Analysis of the stress-strained state has been effected out using a thick beam loaded with distributed load. The beam is composed of layers having anisotropic characteristics E_i , μ_i and b_i , l are its width and length, respectively (Fig. 1).

Let's introduce the condition substance of non-deformability along the direction of y axis on the supposition that $e_y = 0$ /4,5/. As stresses σ_x and σ_y are, in general, other than zero it follows that

$$W(x,y)=w(x) ; \quad \sigma_x = e_x E_x , \quad (1)$$

where W -displacement along the x axis.

Holding that the shearing strain is averaged due to the little thickness h of a beam gives

$$U(x,y) = u(x) + y'\beta(x); \quad y' = y_n - y; \quad \beta(x) = \gamma_{xy}(x) - dW(x) / dx, \quad (2)$$

where u and w is a displacement of a neutral plane along the direction of x and y axis, respectively, β is an angle of rotation cross-section, and y_n is the position of a neutral plane of a beam under bending. The position of a neutral layer for a multilayered beam is determined by the expression

$$y_n = S_z / B, \quad (3)$$

where $S_z = \int_B y \, dB$ - a static moment of a cross-section taking into account the elasticity modulus of the each layer E_{xi} ;

$B = \int_A E_x \, dA$ stiffness of a cross-section at axial load. Here A is an area of the layer's cross - section. To determine the coordinate of a neutral layer at bending a multi-layered beam, one has to know the stiffness and geometrical dimensions of each layer. Stiffness of a cross-section at bending is described by an expression:

$$D_z = \sum_{i=1}^n E_{xi} I_{zi}, \quad (4)$$

where I_{zi} is an inertia moment of each layer with respect to the neutral plane. Under the operation of the axial force and bending moment we'll have

$$\sigma_{xi} = E_{xi} (N / B + y_i' M_z / D_z), \quad (5)$$

where $y_i' = y_n - y_i$.

Dependences (3) and (4) are very handy for the stiffness determination of any number of units and layers geometry of different modules operating at bending as well as at axial load. Calculation results are well agrees with the data obtained using the more complex mathematical apparatus, including the method of finite elements /6/.

A general, shear stress is described by an expression

$$\tau_{xy} = Q_y / (B D_z) \int_0^y b E_x y' dy. \quad (6)$$

The integral represents a sum of static moments below the investigated section relative to neutral plane multiplied by an elastic modulus of a respective layer. Beam shear stiffness can be written down in the form of

$$K = h D_z [\int_0^h (\int_0^y b E_x y' dy) / (b G_{xy}) dy]^{-1}. \quad (7)$$

Experimental stress-strain diagram usually has the shape as shown in Fig.2. To bring it to the shape more handy for engineering calculations, the deformation curve is sketched with the help of polygonal approximation for eight zones; though two straight lines describing a definite zone of tension and compression are enough to determine the stiffness of substances with different modules /7/. As follows from Fig. 2., the actual stresses can be determined by the expression

$$\sigma_Q = \sigma_{s(k)} + E_{s(k)} (e_x - e_{s(k)}), \quad (8)$$

where $E_{s(k)}$ is a true modulus of the layer elasticity in the k range.

3. CALCULATION OF THIN-WALLED BEAMS WITH A MULTI-CELLS CIRCUIT OF CROSS-SECTION

A thin-walled composite beam is made of composite panels. The panels have orthotropic characteristics in their plane and are oriented with respect to beam axes in such a way that one axis of orthotropy is parallel to the beam axis. Panels thickness is small if compare it with the cross-section dimensions. In the cross-section only axial normal stresses operate. Shells are affected by bending moments, shear forces and moments of torsion and operate as thin-walled beams. Geometrical dimensions and character of loading are shown in Fig. 3.

We must indicate that the calculation of shells according to the beam theory can be carried out at stresses exceeding the limit of proportionality and after the stability has been lost. In these cases the calculation is carried out by the method of consecutive approximations, as indicated in section 2.

Determination of normal stresses of the reinforced shell with lining is effected in analogy to the expression (5):

$$\sigma_z = E_z (N_z / B + y_n M_x / D_x - x_n M_y / D_y), \quad (9)$$

where y_n, x_n, D_x, D_y - coordinates of the cross-section and stiffnesses at bending relative to the main central axes x, y of the cross-section, respectively.

There also appear shear stress τ at bending. They are directed towards a contour. To determine the flow of shear forces q , let's single out an element with dimensions $ds dz$ from a shell (Fig. 3.) and analyze its equilibrium maintaining that the surface load is not present in the direction of z axis. Let's project all the forces acting on the element of a shell on axis z . After integrating along s will have:

$$q = \int_0^s (\partial s / \partial z) t ds + q_0(z). \quad (10)$$

Here $q_0(z)$ is a flow of shear forces at point $s=0$. Substituting equation (10) into the normal stresses equation (9) and, taking into account, that in the normal stress equation only M_x and M_y depend on z , gives

$$q = - ((dM_x / dz) S_x / D_x - (dM_y / dz) S_y / D_y) + q_0. \quad (11)$$

Thus, the expression (11) determines stress in all the elements of the contour depending on their actual contribution to the operation of the construction, where

$$S_x = \int_0^s E_z y_n t ds. \quad (12)$$

In analogy to S_y . Functions $S_x(s)$ and $S_y(s)$ are generally static moments multiplied by the modulus of elasticity of the segmented part of the contour of cross-section in the arbitrarily selected system of coordinates xoy (Fig. 3.)

Let's reorganize the equation (11) to its final form. Taking into account the differential dependences between the bending moments and transverse forces we'll have:

$$q = - (Q_y S_x / D_x + Q_x S_y / D_y) + q_0. \quad (13)$$

If elasticity modulus E of the element equals to zero, i.e. there are no normal stresses in the element, then, as it follows from expression (13), q does not appear in it. Thus, the contribution of shear forces is estimated immediately. Flow q_0 that is incorporated in the formula (13) is determined in different ways depending on the degree of the closure of the contour.

To check the truthfulness of the outlined methodics a comparison was drawn between the stiffnesses at bending and torsion of a wing of the glider LAK-17. They were estimated by means of calculation and stiffness tests.

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Figure 1. Scheme of loading of a multi-layered beam.

Figure 2. Non-linear diagram of deformation.

Figure 3. Geometrical dimensions and character of loading of a composite pivot.